

Photochemical Reaction Between Fatty Acids and Chlorine in Carbon Tetrachloride Solutions.

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To elucidate the primary action of light on chlorine and the mechanism of photochemical reactions involving chlorine in solution, one of us (K. P. B.) has already studied the photochemical reaction between cinnamic acid and chlorine (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 341) and between cyclohexane and chlorine (*ibid.*, 1929, 6, 691). The present paper deals with the reaction between some aliphatic compounds (acetic, propionic and *n*-butyric acids) and chlorine.

Benrath and Hertel (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1924, 23, 30) showed that these acids are chlorinated in carbon tetrachloride solutions under stimulus of radiation from a quartz mercury lamp. They performed only one experiment with each acid in white light and the initial concentration of chlorine was about double that of the acids.

We have thoroughly investigated these reactions using different concentrations of the acceptor acids and of chlorine in both white and monochromatic radiation. We have determined the quantum efficiency, temperature coefficient, and dependence on the intensity of incident radiation of these reactions. It might be mentioned at the very beginning that even so far as the kinetics of the reaction is concerned, which was the only thing studied by Benrath and Hertel, we have obtained quite different results.

We might also state that a large amount of experimental work has been done since the work of Steiner in 1874 (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 184) up to the present time (*cf.* Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2067) on the bromination in the dark at a high temperature (1000°) of fatty acids. The reaction appears to be very complex and the final word has not yet been said on the reaction.

On the other hand, as will appear from the present paper, the photo-chlorination of these acids is a relatively simple reaction.

The chlorine solutions in carbon tetrachloride were prepared by a method already recorded (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 341). Purest samples of acetic, propionic and *n*-butyric acids of Kahlbaum were dried over phosphorus pentoxide and redistilled. The reaction

vessel was a cell (4×4×1 cm.) with plane parallel-glass sides. It was placed inside a double jacketted metal-box maintained within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by circulation of water from a thermostat by means of a pump. The reaction cell had a narrow opening at the top provided with a closely fitting stopper. The reaction was followed by pipetting out 2 c.c. from time to time and the chlorine determined iodometrically with *N*/200 or *N*/300-sodium thiosulphate which was prepared afresh and standardised before each experiment.

The Dark Reaction.

In perfectly dry carbon tetrachloride solutions the reaction between chlorine and the acids is negligible at 30.5° in the dark.

TABLE I.

Acetic acid= <i>M</i> /3.	Chlorine= <i>M</i> /64.		Temp.= 30.5° .	
Time in mins.	0	72	860	1200
<i>N</i> /200-Thiosulphate.	12'45	12'45	12'40	12'30 c.c.

The dark reactions in the cases of propionic and butyric acids are also negligible.

The reactions proceeded fairly quickly under stimulus of radiation from a quartz mercury lamp run from a storage battery at a constant current of 3 amperes. The chlorination of acetic acid proceeded most slowly and the rate increased gradually from acetic to butyric acid. The kinetics of the reaction was studied in white light and a glass cell of plane parallel sides, 4 cm. thick and containing water, was placed before the reaction cell. The use of glass-filter and glass-reaction vessel precluded the possibility of decomposition of either carbon tetrachloride or the aliphatic acids by the extreme ultra-violet radiations.

In the chlorination of acetic acid the distance between the mercury lamp and the reaction cell was 10 cm., in the case of propionic acid 14 cm., and in the case of butyric acid 12 cm. In their experiments Benrath and Hertel found an induction period and also found that the reaction followed a course given by the empirical relation $p_t - p_0 = k \log t$ where p_t and p_0 represent the change in chlorine concentration after time t after the lapse of induction period and just after the induction period respectively. We could not detect any appreciable induction period in any of our experiments. We also found the reaction to be perfectly unimolecular

with respect to chlorine. Benrath and Hertel do not mention how they prepared chlorine and some impurity in their chlorine might account for the observed period of induction. The peculiar course of the reaction observed by them might be explained by the fact that the chlorine concentration employed by them being nearly double that of the acceptor acids, all the excited chlorine molecules or atoms formed by absorption of radiation could not find an acceptor molecule to collide and react with. In our experiments the concentration of the chlorine was always less than that of the acceptor acids.

Propionic Acid and Chlorine.

The following table summarises the different results. The value of the unimolecular constant, it will appear, is independent of the concentration of chlorine but increases slightly with increase in concentration of the acceptor. The temperature throughout was maintained at 30.5° and the reaction cell was at a distance of 14 cm. from the mercury lamp. The unimolecular constants throughout this paper are all on the basis of logarithm to the base 10, and the time is reckoned in minutes.

TABLE II.

No.	Conc. of acid.	Conc. of chlorine.	Unimol. const.
1	M/3	M/60	0.00185
2	M/3	M/116	0.00193
3	M/3	M/156	0.00171
4	M/15	M/60	0.00188
5	M/15	M/116	0.00182
6	M/15	M/140	0.00154
7	2M/3	M/60	0.00219
8	M/60	M/60	0.00148

Butyric Acid and Chlorine.

In this case also unimolecular constants were obtained the value of which increased slightly both with increase in the concentration of the acid and of chlorine. The temperature was 30.5° throughout and the distance between the lamp and the reaction cell 19 cm. Table III summarises the different results with butyric acid.

TABLE III.

Conc. of butyric acid.	Conc. of chlorine.	Unimol. const.
<i>M</i> /3	<i>M</i> /60	0·00201
<i>M</i> /3	<i>M</i> /116	0·00190
<i>M</i> /3	<i>M</i> /154	0·00182
<i>M</i> /15	<i>M</i> /60	0·00196
<i>M</i> /15	<i>M</i> /116	0·00154
<i>M</i> /15	<i>M</i> /140	0·00111
2 <i>M</i> /3	<i>M</i> /60	0·00231
<i>M</i> /60	<i>M</i> /60	0·00177

Acetic Acid and Chlorine.

Acetic acid is chlorinated at a much less rapid rate. The unimolecular constant appears to be independent of the initial concentration of chlorine but increases with increase in the concentration of acetic acid. The distance between the lamp and the reaction cell was 10 cm. and the temperature 30·5°. Table IV summarises different results with acetic acid.

TABLE IV.

Conc. of acetic acid.	Conc. of chlorine.	Unimol. const.
<i>M</i> /15	<i>M</i> /50	0·00082
<i>M</i> /15	<i>M</i> /96	0·00080
<i>M</i> /3	<i>M</i> /57	0·00114

Experiments in Monochromatic Light (436 $\mu\mu$)

The same filters were employed to isolate 436 $\mu\mu$ as in the case of the chlorination of cyclohexane. The intensity of the incident radiation was 1·9 Hefners-at-100-cm. The intensity measurements were carried out with a Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer calibrated with a Hefner lamp at a distance of 100 cm. The temperature was 30·5°.

Propionic Acid and Chlorine.

TABLE V.

	Conc. of acid.	Conc. of chlorine.	Unimol const.
1.	<i>M</i> /3	<i>M</i> /56	0·00048
2.	2 <i>M</i> /3	<i>M</i> /62	0·00062

Butyric Acid and Chlorine.

TABLE VI.

	Conc. of acid.	Conc. of chlorine.	Unimol const.
1.	M/3	M/55	0'00101
2.	2M/3	M/62	0'00109

Acetic Acid and Chlorine.

The chlorination of acetic acid under these conditions proceeded very slowly. The following table indicates the change in thiosulphate titre at different intervals.

TABLE VII.

Acetic acid = 2M/3. Chlorine = M/58.					
Time in mins	..	0	66	141	242
/200-Thiosulphate	...	13.9	13'60	18'2	12'8 c.c
Unimol. const.			0'00014	0'00016	0'00014
					Mean 0'00015

Application of Einstein's Law.

The light absorbed by the reacting systems was found by taking galvanometer readings with the reaction cell filled with carbon tetrachloride and then with chlorine solution of requisite strength. 1 Mm. of galvanometer deflection corresponded to an energy of 9 ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

Acetic Acid (Table VII).—The light absorbed corresponded to 27 mm. No. of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per sec.

$$= 27 \times 9 \times \frac{486 \times 10^{-7}}{3 \times 10^{10}} \times \frac{1}{6.5 \times 10^{-27}} = 5.4 \times 10^{13}.$$

The change in chlorine concentration equals 0.3 c.c. of N/200 in 2 c.c. in 66 minutes. No. of molecules transformed per sq. cm. per sec.

$$= \frac{0.3}{2} \times \frac{1}{66 \times 60} \times \frac{1}{400 \times 1000} \times 6.1 \times 10^{23} = 5.7 \times 10^{13}.$$

For every quantum of light (486 $\mu\mu$) absorbed one molecule of chlorine enters into reaction.

Propionic Acid (Table V, 2).—The light absorbed, corresponded to 24 mm. No. of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. therefore $= 4.8 \times 10^{13}$.

No. of mols. transformed per sq. cm. per sec. $= 23.6 \times 10^{13}$.
The quantum efficiency is therefore 5.

Butyric Acid (Table VI, 2).—The light absorbed corresponded to 24 mm.

No. of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. $= 4.8 \times 10^{13}$.
No. of mols. transformed per sq. cm. per sec. $= 38.9 \times 10^{13}$.
The quantum efficiency is therefore 8.

Temperature Coefficient at 436 μ .

A temperature much lower than 25.5° could not be employed as that was found to result in the deposition of moisture. The following experiments were performed at 25.5° and the intensity of incident monochromatic radiation was the same as in the previous experiments. The chlorination of acetic acid being very slow was not attempted at the lower temperature.

TABLE VIII.

Temp. = 25.5°.

Name of acid.	Conc. of acid.	Conc. of chlorine.	Unimol. const.
Propionic ...	M/3	M/58	0.00041
The corresponding value at 30.5° (Table V, 1) is 0.00048			
Butyric ...	M/3	M/82	0.00088
The corresponding value at 30.5° (Table VI, 1) is 0.00101			

The temperature coefficient of propionic acid, therefore, equals $\left(\frac{0.00048}{0.00041}\right)^2 = 1.41$; and the temperature coefficient of butyric acid, therefore, equals $\left(\frac{0.00101}{0.00088}\right)^2 = 1.32$.

Influence of the Intensity of Incident Radiation.

Butyric Acid. A lower intensity of monochromatic radiation (436 μ) was employed than in the case of Table VI, 2. The ratio

of the intensities in Table VI, 2 and Table IX was, as found by galvanometer deflections equal to $\left(\frac{188}{128}\right) = 1.47$.

Table IX gives the result at the lower intensity.

TABLE IX.

Butyric Acid. Intensity of incident radiation ($486\mu\mu$) = 1.28 Hefners-at 100 cm. Temp. = 30.5° .

Conc. of acid. 2M/3	Conc. of chlorine. M/54	Unimol. const. 0.00070
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The ratio of the velocity constants is thus $= \frac{0.00109}{0.00070} = 1.56$.

The reaction is, therefore, directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation.

Propionic Acid. As the reaction is a slower one, a lower intensity of monochromatic light was not employed. The reaction was carried out in a lower intensity of white light than in Table II, 7. The ratio of the intensities in Table II, 7 and Table X as found by galvanometer deflections with a resistance of 200 ohms in series, was $\frac{274}{188} = 2.0$. Table X gives the reaction at a lower intensity of white light.

TABLE X.

Propionic Acid.

Intensity of incident radiation = 1.88 Hefners. Temp. = 30.5° .

Conc. of acid. 2M/3	Conc. of chlorine. M/99	Unimol. const. 0.00118
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The mean constant at the higher intensity was 0.00219. The ratio of the constants is thus $\frac{0.00219}{0.00118} = 1.86$. The reaction is thus directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation,

Acetic Acid. The reaction is so slow that a lower intensity of white light even could not be employed. From analogy it might be expected that the relation will be the same in this case as well.

Theoretical.

The main features of these reactions are similar to those in the case of cinnamic acid and cyclohexane. The temperature coefficient and the influence of the intensity of incident radiation are the same. These chlorinations are not, however, affected by the increasing concentration of hydrochloric acid which is continually generated as a result of reaction. This is remarkable since the bromination of these acids in the dark at high temperatures has been shown by various investigators (*cf.* Watson, *loc. cit.*) to be markedly accelerated by acids. This shows that the mechanism of the photo-chlorination is fundamentally different from the bromination in the dark.

The primary action of effective radiation ($\lambda=4785\text{\AA}$) is, as has been abundantly made clear in the previous communications, is the dissociation of chlorine molecule into an excited and a normal atom as indicated below.

Indicating an acceptor molecule of acid by HA the following reaction then takes place.

If we assume, as has been done in previous communications that the reverse action $\text{Cl} + \text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{Cl}_2$ is extremely slow compared to reaction (2), we can very easily explain the unimolecular nature of the constant and its direct proportionality with the intensity of incident radiation. Assuming, therefore, that the velocity of reaction is essentially governed by the rate of production of chlorine atoms, we have

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = KI_0(1 - e^{-\epsilon cd}) = KI_0 \epsilon cd$$

where I_0 = intensity of incident radiation,

ϵ = extinction coefficient,

c = concentration of chlorine,

d = depth of solution,

when, as was the case in our experiments, the absorption is small,

This demands that the quantum efficiency should be unity. This demand is actually fulfilled in the case of acetic acid. But in the case of propionic and butyric acids the quantum efficiency is slightly higher. This might be due to the fact that greater energy liberated in the two latter cases might initiate some sort of chain reaction.

Summary.

The kinetics of the photo-chlorination of acetic, propionic and *n*-butyric acids have been studied in white as well as in monochromatic light. In all cases unimolecular constants with respect to chlorine are obtained that vary slightly with the concentration of the acceptor.

The unimolecular constant is directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation. The temperature coefficient in blue light (436 $\mu\mu$) is about 1.4 in all cases.

The quantum efficiency is unity in the case of acetic, 5 in the case of propionic and 8 in the case of *n*-butyric acids.

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